

SEMANTICS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN THE STRUCTURE OF PROPER NOUNS

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Annotation: This article analyzes the semantics of phraseological units within proper nouns. The semantics of phraseological units activate not only the real object but also the historical and cultural context.

Key words: national thought, symbolic center, figurative images, cultural connotation, historical consciousness, symbolic-figurative, cultural icon

INTRODUCTION

It is known that phraseological units are linguistic units that make up the vocabulary of each language and they exist as linguistic units ready for speech. The meanings that are understood from a free connection and a phraseological unit that are similar in form to each other are not considered polysemy when combined into one point. Through such units, the historical and cultural memory of the people, the system of social ideals and values, is expressed, and their semantics is formed not only by linguistic, but also by linguocultural, psycholinguistic and sociocognitive factors. The semantics of phraseological units involving proper nouns shows that they are related not only to their external structure, but also to their internal figurative meaning, cultural connotation, emotional-associative impact, as well as to their historical, mythological, and religious foundations in popular thought. It is precisely these aspects that make this topic extremely important from a scientific point of view and worthy of in-depth study.

METHODS

This research employs a comparative-descriptive method, analyzing examples from modern English and Uzbek grammars, dictionaries, and academic sources. Proper nouns are classified into several categories:

1. Historical-referential semantics
2. Symbolic-figurative semantics

3. Evaluative/emotional semantics

Such phraseologisms are actively used in folk art, literature, historical epics, and political and social discourse.

RESULTS

In foreign linguistics, the semantic properties of phraseological units have attracted the attention of many researchers. In particular, G. Palmer interprets phraseological units as a “semantic block encoding existing reality” and emphasizes that they embody national thinking, cultural stereotypes, and historical memory. Also, A. Wierzbicka, introducing the concept of “cultural keywords” in semantic analysis, connects units involving proper nouns with spiritual criteria, aesthetic concepts, and social ideals inherent in the people. R. Gläser, studying the semantic motivation of phraseological units, proved that proper nouns serve as a symbolic center in their structure, through which a ready-made image awakens in the reader's mind. Such units as “Achilles’ heel”, “Midas touch”, “Scrooge mentality” in English are a vivid example of this. According to R. Gläser, these units activate cultural memory through linguosemantic fields and also embody pragmatic evaluation. In Uzbek linguistics, important studies have also been carried out on the semantic properties of phraseological units with proper nouns. In particular, B. Yuldoshev emphasizes in his studies that such units express the spiritual world of the people through a system of figurative images and a moral-spiritual approach

Historical-referential semantics is a form of meaning that arises through the reference of a proper noun in a phraseological unit to a specific historical person, place, event or period

For example:

- “Temur tuzuklariga amal qilmoq” - this expression refers to the political and military regulations of Amir Timur;

- “Shoh Jahon izidan yurmoq” - a reference to the history of architecture;

Such phraseologisms are actively used in folk oral literature, literature, historical epics, and political and social discourse.

- Napoleon complex – “He acted like he had a Napoleon complex.”

- Caesar’s ambition – “His downfall was Caesar’s ambition repeating itself.”

Symbolic-figurative semantics is a layer of meaning that is formed not directly through the proper nouns in a phraseological unit, but through images and symbols.

For example: In Uzbek:

- “Rustamdek kurashmoq” – The name Rustam symbolizes courage, strength, and will;

- “Scrooge mentality” – becomes a symbol of stinginess and coldness;

In English:

- Scrooge mentality – “His Scrooge mentality ruined the party spirit.”

- Achilles’ heel – “His kindness was his Achilles’ heel.”

Evaluative/emotional semantics is a semantic layer that expresses the subjective attitude, social assessment or emotional state of the speaker using proper nouns in a phraseological unit. For example:

- “Zulfiyaxonim mehribonligi bilan yondashmoq” — an expression of sincerity, respect;

- “Like a Scrooge” — a critical assessment, a hint of coldness and stinginess;

Such units are based on subjective perception and have different emotional effects in different contexts. Units of this type are actively used in education, the media, literature, politics, art, and everyday speech and are understood through the cultural competence of the reader or listener.

DISCUSSION

In phraseological units of historical – referential semantics the proper noun is directly or indirectly related to the historical context and reminds the reader of a specific period, person or event. This type of semantics performs not only a denotative (reference to a real object), but also a function that activates historical-cultural memory.

In Symbolic-figurative semantics, the name of a person or place leaves its original historical-referential function and becomes a symbol, a generalized image, accepted in culture. In such phraseological units, the proper noun serves as a symbol of typical behavior, universal characters or moral-aesthetic values

Through the evaluative/emotional semantics of semantics, the speaker expresses his point of view, expresses his opinion with melodiousness, irony, affection, pity or criticism. In such units, proper nouns serve as a moral criterion, social image or form of emotional expression.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, phraseological meaning is a complex, holistic unity that can be studied using component analysis. Connotative meaning plays an important role in the meaning of phraseological units. Connotation is determined by emotionality, intellectual and/or emotional assessment, expressiveness, as well as functional-stylistic or communicative-stylistic connection and the national-cultural component of connotation, which is most clearly manifested in phraseological units with an integrative component. The uniqueness of phraseological units is also associated with their internal form. In our study, the internal form means the associative-figurative motivational complex that forms the content in the language.

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